

On the cave spiders of Georgia with description of a new blind *Centromerus* (Arachnida: Araneae)

Christo Deltshev¹, Shalva Barjadze², Eter Maghradze³

(1) Natural Museum of Natural History, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, 1 Tsar Osoboditel Blvd, 1000 Sofia, Bulgaria, deltshev@gmail.com ✉; <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0539-5673> 🔗

(2) Ilia State University, Institute of Zoology, Giorgi Tsereteli 3, 0162 Tbilisi, Georgia, shalva.barjadze@yahoo.com ✉; <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8992-4987> 🔗

(3) Ilia State University, Institute of Zoology, Giorgi Tsereteli 3, 0162 Tbilisi, Georgia, eter.maghradze@yahoo.com ✉; <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4796-9439> 🔗

<https://zoobank.org/86E63D5F-9D89-4286-8E05-9A3DED003985> 🔗

Abstract: A new species *Centromerus georgicus* sp. n. collected in a Georgian cave (Caucasus) is described based on male and female specimens, diagnosed, and illustrated. New records of some poorly known species (*Tegenaria pontica* Haritonov, 1947, *Dysdera anatoliae* Deeleman-Reinhold, 1988 and *Leptonetela caucasica* Dunin 1990), as well as the description of the unknown female of *L. caucasica* are also presented.

Keywords: Caucasus, *Dysdera*, *Leptonetela*, new species, *Tegenaria*

Introduction

The first information about spiders in the caves of Georgia was published by Reimoser (1930) followed by Spassky (1932) and Charitonov (1939, 1941a, 1941b, 1946, 1947, 1956). Charitonov (1941a) divides the distinct zoogeographical group of the Caucasian troglobite spiders into two sub-groups: Pontic group and Abkhazian group. The first summarising data about Georgian spiders was published in the monograph ‘Georgian spiders’ in which Mcheidze (1997) reported 362 spider species found on the territory of Georgia. Most recent papers on Georgian cave spiders are those of Dunin (1990), Marusic & Guseinov (2003), Ponomarev & Chumachenko (2007), Kovblyuk et al. (2011) and Otto (2022).

The aim of the present study is to provide information on accumulating data on recently collected spiders in Georgian caves and description of a blind *Centromerus* species.

Material and methods

The studied material was collected by hand picking. Colouration is described from alcohol preserved specimens. Measurements of the legs were taken from the dorsal side. Total length of the body includes the chelicerae. All measurements are in mm. Specimens were examined and measured using a Wild M5A stereomicroscope. Digital images were taken with a Canon EOS1100 attached to a Carl Zeiss Amplitval microscope and processed using Adobe Photoshop CS6 software. The specimens are preserved in 70–95% ethanol and deposited in Institute of Zoology, Tbilisi (IZISU), Natural History Museum Stuttgart (NHMS) and National Museum of Natural History, Sofia (NMNHS). The nomenclature follows the World Spider Catalog (World Spider Catalog, 2023) and the taxa are listed alphabetically.

Abbreviations (follow Ballarin & Pantini, 2020): AER – anterior eye row; ALE – anterior lateral eyes; APP – anterio-proximal part of the median

Figs 1–4. *Tegenaria pontica*: (1) sternum; (2) epigyne; (3, 4) epigyne/vulva ventral/dorsal view. Scale bars – Fig. 1 – 0.6 mm; Figs 2–4 – 0.1 mm.

membrane; AW – anterior wall of the epigyne; CG – copulatory grooves; CO – copulatory opening; DS – distal part of scapus; DT – distal tubercle (dorsal hump) of the cymbium; E – embolus; LAW – lateral lobes of the anterior wall; MM – median membrane; MT – median tubercle of the cymbium; P – paracymbium; PER – posterior eyes row; PLE – posterior lateral eyes; PME – posterior median eyes; PMP – posterior median plate; R – radix; RA (I-II) – radical apophyses; S – spermatheca; SA – distal suprategular apophysis; TA – terminal apophysis.

Results

Agelenidae

Tegenaria pontica Charitonov, 1947

Material. 2 ♀♀ (NHMS), Samegrelo-Zemo Svaneti Region, Martvili Municipality, Odishi Karst Massif, Inchkhuri Cave, 18.V.2022, S. Barjadze, A. Faille, E. Maghradze leg.

Figs 5–8. *Dysdera anatoliae*: (5) epigyne; (6–8) epigyne/vulva ventral/dorsal view. Scale bars – Fig. 5 – 0.3 mm; Figs 6–8 – 0.2 mm.

Distribution: Georgia (Otto, 2022; World Spider Catalog, 2023) (Fig. 23).

Remarks. Known only from type locality (Phanagoria Cave) (Otto, 2022). Our specimen is either identical or closely related to *T. pontica* and corresponds with the description and single drawing published so far. Here we provide photographs of sternum and epigyne/vulva that correspond with the single figure in the description of the species (Figs 1–4).

Dysderidae

Dysdera anatoliae Deeleman-Reinhold, 1988
Figs 5–8

Material. 1 ♀, 1 juv. (NHMS), Racha-Lechkhumi-Kvemo Svaneti Region, Ambrolauri Municipality, Racha Karst Massif, Dolabistavi Cave, 25.V.2022, S. Barjadze, A. Faille, A. Maghradze leg.

Distribution: Turkey (World Spider Catalog, 2023), Georgia (this paper) (Fig. 23).

Remarks. Known only from type locality (North Anatolia) (Deeleman & Reinhold, 1988). Our specimen is either identical or closely related to *D. anatoliae* and corresponds with the description and drawings published so far. Here we provide photographs of eyes and epigyne/vulva that correspond with the figures in the description of the species (Figs 5–8).

Leptonetidae

Leptonetela caucasica Dunin, 1990
Figs 9–14

Material. 2 ♂♂, 3 ♀♀ (NHMS), Samegrelo-Zemo Svaneti Region, Martvili Municipality, Odishi Karst Massif, Inchkhuri Cave, 18.V.2022, S. Barjadze, A. Faille, E. Maghradze leg.

Figs 9–14. *Leptonetela caucasica*: (9, 10) male palp, retrolateral/prolateral view; (11) tuft of hairs on Mt III; (12) internal genitalia; (13, 14) habitus, dorsal/ventral view. Scale bars – Figs 9, 10 – 0.1 mm; Fig. 11 – 0.2 mm; Fig. 12 – 0.08 mm; Figs 13, 14 – 0.4 mm.

Distribution: Georgia – North Caucasus (Otto, 2022; World Spider Catalog, 2023) (Fig. 23).

Remarks. The species was described by Dunin (1990) from a male, collected in detritus of beech forest in the North Caucasus. Marusik & Guseinov (2003) presented the description of a female of *L. caucasica* from Azerbaijan with the remark, that the identification is very provisional and the single female may be preferable refer to the Turkish *L. deltshevi* (Brignoli, 1979) or to an undescribed species. The present material (male/female) is found in a cave but is identical both in habitus and structures of the palp and corresponds completely with the descriptions and all available drawings published so far (Figs 9–11). The collected undescribed female gives the possibility to ameliorate the description.

Description of female: Measurements: Total length 1.98; cephalothorax length 0.72, width 0.65; sternum length 0.48, width 0.40; clypeus 0.10; chelicerae length 0.32, width 0.14; eyes ALE 0.07, PLE 0.04, PME 0.07; ALE-PME 0.04, PLE-PLE 0.04, PLE-PME 0.05, AER 0.15, PER 0.1; abdomen 1.10; legs: I – 4.32 (1.26, 0.18, 1.22, 0.86, 0.79); II – 3.38 (0.90, 0.18, 0.97, 0.72, 0.61); III – 2.92 (0.83, 0.18, 0.79, 0.61, 0.50); IV – 4.18 (1.26, 0.18, 1.19, 0.83, 0.72).

Colouration. Carapace pale brown, median groove needle shaped. Chelicerae brown with nine promarginal cheliceral teeth. Endites and labium brown. Sternum pale brown. Legs yellow to pale yellow. Abdomen grey to pale grey (Figs 13, 14).

Genital area covered with short hairs, spermathecae slightly visible. Internal genitalia with a pair of spermathecae and sperm ducts, atrium fusiform (Fig. 12).

Linyphiidae

Centromerus georgicus Deltshv **sp. n.**

Figs 15–23

urn:lsid:zoobank.org:act:

[BD0B0D4F-6B40-4787-A47C-9575BDF15C1A](https://zoobank.org/BD0B0D4F-6B40-4787-A47C-9575BDF15C1A)

Material. Holotype ♂ (IZISU), Imereti Region, Tskaltubo Municipality, Sataplia-Tskaltubo Karst Massif, Melouri Cave, 1.XII.2018, E. Maghradze leg. Paratypes: 2 ♀♀ (IZISU), 1 ♀ (NMNHS) same data

as holotype; 1 ♂ (NMNHS), same locality as holotype, 30.X.2018, E. Maghradze leg.

Comparative material examined: *Centromerus bulgarianus* Drensky, 1931, 1 ♂ lectotype, 3 ♀♀ paralectotypes, Bulgaria, Lakatnik Village, Suhata Pester Cave, P. Drensky leg (NMNHS); *Centromerus dacicus* Dumitresco, 1980, 4 ♀♀, Romania, Closhani Cave, 18.II.2020, A. Nae leg (NMNHS); *Centromerus serbicus* Deltshv, 2002, 1 ♂, 1 ♀, Serbia, Zlot, Beljavina Village, Mandina Cave, 27.V.2012, D. Antić & S. Ćurčić leg. (NMNHS).

Diagnosis. *Centromerus georgicus* sp. n. is a blind species and belongs to europaeus species group of *Centromerus* (Deltshv, & Ćurčić 1997). The new species is closely related to *C. bulgarianus* Drensky, 1931, *C. dacicus* Dumitrescu & Georgescu, 1980 and *C. serbicus* Deltshv, 2002, distinguished from them by the following differential features: *C. serbicus* is larger (1.8/2.16), followed by *C. bulgarianus* (1.64/1.74), *C. georgicus* sp. n. (1.44/1.46) and *C. dacicus* (1.32/1.57) (Dumitrescu & Georgescu, 1980; Deltshv, 1973, 1997; Deltshv & Ćurčić, 2002); the terminal apophyses are similar but in *C. georgicus* sp. n. is the straightest, while in the other species it is more or less curved apically (Fig. 17) (Deltshv & Ćurčić, 2002); radical apophyses (I-II) are also similar but in *C. bulgarianus* the heel of R II is more pointed at the end, elliptical in *C. georgicus* sp. n. and more or less spherical in *C. dacicus* and *C. serbicus* (Figs 15–18) (Deltshv & Ćurčić, 2002); antero-proximal parts of the median membranes are similar but differ in details, with slightly toothed margin in *C. georgicus* sp. n. and *C. bulgarianus* and covered with small teeth along its entire length in *C. dacicus* and *C. serbicus* (Figs 16, 18) (Deltshv & Ćurčić, 2002); females are almost indistinguishable but the spermathecae in *C. georgicus* sp. n. are the smallest than in the other species and the posterior median plate has a horizontal upper edge (Figs 19–22) (Deltshv & Ćurčić, 2002).

Etymology. The species name is derived from Georgia.

— Description

Male holotype. Measurements: Total length 1.44; cephalothorax length 0.65, width 0.54; sternum length 0.32, width 0.32; chelicerae length 0.25, width 0.10; eye absent; abdomen length 0.80; legs: I – 3.38 (0.97, 0.18, 0.90, 0.72, 0.61); II – 3.06 (0.90, 0.18, 0.79, 0.65, 0.54); III – 2.66 (0.68, 0.18, 0.72, 0.58,

Figs 15–22. *Centromerus georgicus* sp. n.: (15, 16) left male palp external/internal view; (17, 18) left male palp external/internal view; (19, 20) epigyne/vulva ventral/dorsal view; (21, 22) epigyne/vulva ventral/dorsal view. Scale bars – Figs 15–18 – 0.1 mm; Figs 19–22 – 0.04 mm.

Fig. 23. Distributional map of the caves sampled spiders in Georgia: 1 – Letsurtsume Cave, 2 – Kakaro I Cave, 3 – Kakaro III Cave, 4 – Motena Cave, 5 – Inchkhuri Cave, 6 – Melouri Cave, 7 – Khomuli Cave, 8 – Sataplia Cave, 9 – Tsutskhvati Cave Complex, 10 – Gogolati (= Tsakhi) Cave, 11 – Sagvarjile Cave, 12 – Sakishore Cave, 13 – Dolabistavi Cave, 14 – Taroklde Cave, 15 – Khvedelidzeebisklde Cave.

0.50); IV – 3.35 (0.97, 0.18, 0.90, 0.72, 0.58).
 Colouration: Chelicerae yellow brown, armed with 3 teeth on outer row and 3 denticles on inner row.

Carapace and sternum yellow. Abdomen pale-yellow.
 Legs yellow to pale yellow, femora I with a prolateral spine in apical half; tibiae II-III with 2 dorsal spines;

tibia IV with 1 dorsal spine: metatarsi I-II with 1 small dorsal spine.

Palp (Figs 15–18): Cymbium with distal tubercle. Paracymbium large with serrated inner margin and 6 short hairs near proximal end. Two proximal radical apophyses, one short and robust, the other long, curved with a small heel-like appendage apically. Distal suprategular apophysis long, slightly curved and robust. Antero-proximal part of median membrane with a row of small, blunt teeth. Terminal apophysis transparent and scarcely visible. Embolus massive, curved, pointed apically.

Female (paratype). Measurements: Total length 1.46; cephalothorax length 0.61, width 0.54; sternum length 0.32, width 0.32; chelicerae length 0.25, width 0.10; eyes absent; abdomen 0.83; Legs: I – 3.13 (0.90, 0.18, 0.79, 0.72, 0.54); II – 2.80 (0.76, 0.18, 0.76, 0.58, 0.54); III – 2.45 (0.68, 0.18, 0.61, 0.54, 0.43); IV – 3.31 (0.90, 0.18, 1.15, 0.65, 0.47).

Colouration as in male.

Epigyne/Vulva (Figs 19–22): Anterior wall triangular, strongly wrinkled, covering a large epigynal cavity, ending with elongated truncated, squared tip. Distal part of scapus wide and rounded. Posterior median plate small and rectangular, with a triangular extension in the middle pointed to distal part, longer than wide. Spermathecae elongated comma-shaped. Copulatory ducts turning arcuate posteriorly and outward before returning to the middle part of the vulva, ending in copulatory openings in the distal part of the scapus.

Ecology. *C. georgicus* sp. n. inhabits the dark zone of the cave and can be regarded as a troglobite species (sensu Sket, 2008).

Distribution. Known only from the type locality in Caucasus Mts, Georgia (Fig. 23).

Remarks. *C. georgicus* sp. n., *C. bulgarianus*, *C. dacicus* and *C. serbicus* are closely allied and strictly vicariant species forming a superspecies. All these taxa are similar, they have limited ranges and probably, represent the descendants of a common ancestor; it is assumed that this ancestral form is no longer present in the epigeal fauna and that it has been replaced by an extant *Centromerus* (Deltshv & Ćurčić, 1997).

Porrhomma convexum (Westring, 1851)

Material. 1 ♀ (NMNHS) Georgia, Imereti Region, Tskaltubo Municipality, near Banodja Village,

Sataplia I Cave, 407 m, 22.VII.2006, S. Lazarov, P. Stoev leg.

Distribution: Palaearctic (World Spider Catalog, 2023).

Remarks. First record for Georgian caves.

Nesticidae

Aituaria borutzkyi (Reimoser, 1930)

Material. 3 ♂♂, 2 ♀♀, 2 juv. (NHMS) Imereti Region, Tskaltubo Municipality, Sataplia-Tskaltubo Karst Massif, Khomuli Cave; 3 ♂♂, 2 ♀♀ (NHMS) Imereti Region, Chiatura Municipality, near Zodi Village, Khvedelidzeebisklde Cave; 3 ♀♀ (NHMS) Imereti Region, Chiatura Municipality, near Zodi Village, Zemo Imereti Plateau, Taroklde Cave; 1 ♀ (NHMS) Imereti Region, Tskaltubo Municipality, Okriba Karst Massif, Tsutskhvati Cave Complex; 1 ♀ (NHMS) Racha-Lechkhumi-Kvemo Svaneti Region, Ambrolauri Municipality, Racha Karst Massif, Dolabistavi Cave; 2 juv. (NHMS) Racha-Lechkhumi-Kvemo Svaneti Region, Ambrolauri Municipality, Racha Karst Massif, Sakishore Cave; 1 ♀ (NHMS) Racha-Lechkhumi-Kvemo Svaneti Region, Ambrolauri Municipality, Racha Karst Massif, Gogolati (=Tsakhi) Cave; 1 juv. (NHMS) Samegrelo-Zemo Svaneti Region, Martvili Municipality, Askhi Karst Massif, Motena Cave, 21.V.2022; 2 ♂♂, 1 ♀, 2 juv. (NHMS) Samegrelo-Zemo Svaneti Region, Chkhorotsku Municipality, Letsurtsume Cave, 20.V.2022; 2 ♂♂, 2 juv. (NHMS) Samegrelo-Zemo Svaneti Region, Chkhorotsku Municipality, Odishi Karst Massif, Nogha Village, Kakaro I Cave, 18.V.2022; 2 ♂♂, 4 ♀♀, 5 juv. (NHMS) Samegrelo-Zemo Svaneti Region, Chkhorotsku Municipality, Odishi Karst Massif, Nogha Village, Kakaro III Cave, 21.V.2022; 7 juv. (NHMS) Samegrelo-Zemo Svaneti Region, Martvili Municipality, Odishi Karst Massif, Inchkhuri Cave, 8.V.2022 (S. Barjadze, A. Faille, E. Maghradze leg.); 2 ♂♂, 3 ♀♀, 3 juv. (NMNHS) Imereti Region, Tskaltubo Municipality, near Banodja Village, Sataplia-Tskaltubo Karst Massif, Sataplia I Cave, 407 m, 22.VII.2006; 3 ♀♀, 3 juv., (NMNHS) Imereti Region, Terjola Village, DzevriVillage, Water Power Station Sagvarjile, Okriba Karst Massif, Sagvarjile Cave, 232 m, 22.VII.2006, (P. Stoev & S. Lazarov leg.).

Distribution: Georgia, Turkey and Ukraine (World Spider Catalog, 2023) (Fig. 23).

Remarks. *A. borutzkyi* was described by Reimoser (1930) until now known from 4 caves in the Caucasus. The new reported localities except Sataplia I Cave are new for the species.

Pholcidae

Holocnemus pluchei (Scopoli, 1763)

Material. 1 ♀, Georgia, Racha-Lechkhumi-Kvemo Svaneti Region, Ambrolauri Municipality, Racha Karst Massif, Dolabistavi Cave, 25.V.2022, S. Barjadze, A. Faille, E. Maghradze leg.

Distribution: Europe, North Africa, Turkey, Caucasus, Middle East. Introduced to USA, Argentina, Japan, Australia (World Spider Catalog, 2023) (Fig. 23).

Remarks. First report for the caves of Georgia.

Tetragnatidae

Metellina merianae (Scopoli, 1763)

Material. 1 ♀ (NMNHS) Georgia, Imereti Region, Tskaltubo Municipality, Banodja Village, Sataplia-Tskaltubo Karst Massif, Sataplia I Cave, 407 m, 22.VII.2006, S. Lazarov & P. Stoev leg.; 1 ♀ (NMNHS) Georgia, Imereti Region, Terjola Municipality, Dzevri Village, Water Power Station Sagvarjile, Sagvarjile Cave, 232 m, 22.VII.2006, P. Stoev & S. Lazarov leg.

Distribution: Europe to Central Asia (World Spider Catalog, 2023) (Fig. 23).

Remarks. *M. merianae* is widespread in the caves, the new reported caves are new localities for the species in Georgia.

Acknowledgments

We are grateful to colleagues who provided us with material for this study (alphabetically): Arnaud Faille (Stuttgart, Germany), Augustin Nae (Bucurest, Romania), Dragan Antić (Belgrad, Serbia), Pavel Stoev and Stoyan Lazarov (Sofia, Bulgaria). Many thanks to Martina Pavlek (Zagreb, Croatia) and

Dragan Chobanov (Sofia, Bulgaria) for their valuable comments on the manuscript and to Boyan Zlatkov (Sofia, Bulgaria) for the valuable help by preparing of digital images. This study was supported by the projects: “Cybertaxonomic approach to phylogenetic studies of model invertebrate genera (Invertebrata, Arachnida, Insecta) clarifying the problems of origin, formation and conservation of the Invertebrate Fauna of the Balkan Peninsula” – National Science Fund, Ministry of Education, Youth and Science of the Republic of Bulgaria, Grant KP-06-H21/1-17.12.2018, “Biodiversity and Evolution of cave fauna of Caucasus (Georgia)” (DFG FA 1042/2-1) and the Conservation Leadership Programme (CLP) grant: “Conservation actions and invertebrates investigations in Sataplia-Tskaltubo karst caves, Georgia”.

References

- Ballarin F., Pantini P. 2020 Three new species and new records of the genus *Centromerus* (Araneae, Linyphiidae) from Italy. *European Journal of Taxonomy* 660: 1–23.
- Charitonov D.E. 1939 [On the cave spiders of Abkhasia]. *Izdatelstvo Gruzinskogo filiala AN SSSR, Tbilisi*, 197–211. (In Russian)
- Charitonov D.E. 1941a [New materials on the Arachnoidea of Abkhasia caves]. *Trudy Zoologicheskogo instituta AN Gruzinskoy SSR* 4: 165–175. (In Russian)
- Charitonov D.E. 1941b [On the cave fauna of Caucasus]. *Izvestiya Biologicheskogo NII pri Permskom universitete* 12 (2): 67–72. (In Russian)
- Charitonov D.E. 1946 [Arachnoidea from the Sataple Cave (Kutaisi)]. *Soobshcheniya AN Gruzunskoy SSR* 7 (3): 145–147. (In Russian)
- Charitonov D.E. 1947 [Spiders and harvestspiders from the caves of the Black Sea coast of the Caucasus]. *Byulleten Moskovskogo Obshchestva Ispytateley Prirody* 52 (1): 15–28. (In Russian)
- Charitonov D.E. 1956 [Overview of the spider family Dysderidae in the fauna of the USSR]. *Uchenye zapiski Permskogo universiteta* 10 (1): 17–39. (In Russian)
- Deeleman-Reinhold C.L., Deeleman P.R. 1988 Revision des Dysderinae (Araneae, Dysderidae), les espèces méditerranéennes occidentales

- exceptées. Tijdschrift voor Entomologie 131: 141–269.
- Deltshv C. 1973 Redescription of *Centromerus bulgarianus* (Drensky 1931) and *Centromerus lakatnikensis* (Drensky 1931) (Araneae, Linyphiidae). International Journal of Speleology 5: 117–126.
- Deltshv C., Ćurčić B.P.M. 1997 Contribution to the knowledge of the group *europaeus* of *Centromerus* Dahl (Linyphiidae, Araneae) in the Balkan Peninsula. Revue suisse de Zoologie 104 (1): 49–55.
- Deltshv C., Ćurčić B.P.M. 2002 A contribution to the study of the genus *Centromerus* Dahl (Araneae: Linyphiidae) in caves of the Balkan Peninsula. Revue suisse de Zoologie 109 (1): 167–176.
- Dumitrescu M., Georgescu M. 1980 Quelques espèces du genre *Centromerus* (Araneae, Linyphiidae) trouvées en Roumanie. Travaux de l'Institut de Spéologie "Émile Racovitza" 19: 103–123.
- Dunin P.M. 1990 *Leptonetela caucasica* sp. n. – a first finding of spiders of the family Leptonetidae (Aranei, Haplogynae) in the USSR. Zoologicheskii Zhurnal 69 (1): 147–149.
- Kovblyuk M.M., Marusik Y.M., Ponomarev A.V., Gnelitsa V.A., Nadolny A.A. 2011 Spiders (Arachnida: Aranei) of Abkhazia. Arthropoda Selecta 20 (1): 21–56.
- Marusik Y.M., Guseinov E.F. 2003 Spiders (Arachnida: Aranei) of Azerbaijan. 1. New family and genus records. Arthropoda Selecta 12: 29–46.
- Mcheidze T. 1997 Spiders of Georgia: Systematics, Ecology, Zoogeographic Review. Tbilisi University, Tbilisi, 390 pp. (In Georgian)
- Otto S. 2022 Caucasian Spiders. A Faunistic Database on the Spiders of the Caucasus Ecoregion. Database version 02.2022. <https://caucasus-spiders.info/> .
- Ponomarev A.V., Chumachenko Y.A. 2007 Arachnida in Ground Mesofauna of Yewbox Grove of the Caucasian Biospheric Reserve. Studies of the Southern Scientific Centre of the Russian Academy of Sciences III: Biodiversity and Transformation of Mountain Ecosystems of Caucasus. SSC RAS Publishing, Rostov-on-Don, 151–163.
- Reimoser E. 1930 Eine neue *Nesticus*-Art aus dem Kaukasus. Zoologischer Anzeiger 88: 158–159.
- Sket B. 2008 Can we agree on an ecological classification of subterranean animals? Journal of Natural History 42: 21–22.
- Spassky S. 1932 Aranearum species novae II. Bulletin du Muséum d'histoire naturelle Paris (Ser. 2) 4 (8): 972–979.
- World Spider Catalog 2023 World Spider Catalog. Version 24.5. Natural History Museum Bern. <https://wsc.nmbe.ch> .